

PHENOXIDES OF MANGANESE

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The phenoxides of manganese have been prepared by (i) heating anhydrous manganous chloride with the respective phenol and (ii) mixing the aqueous solutions of sodium salt of the phenol and manganous chloride; the properties of the phenoxides have been studied.

A review of the literature shows that practically no work has been done on the phenoxides of manganese. Cronheim (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1947, 12, 11) observed the formation of a strongly coloured metal salt by shaking a solution of *o*-nitrosophenol in petroleum ether with an aqueous solution of manganous chloride and believed in its existence as two types of compounds: (a) $C_6H_4NO_2 \cdot MnCl_2$ and (b) $C_6H_4 \cdot NO \cdot OMnO \cdot NOC_6H_4$. The present investigation was therefore undertaken with a view to studying the preparation and properties of some phenoxides of manganese.

EXPERIMENTAL

The phenols used were of B.D.H. pure quality. Anhydrous manganous chloride was obtained by passing dry hydrogen chloride over hydrated manganous chloride at about 160°.

(a) *Preparation in dry state.*—The phenol and manganous chloride were mixed thoroughly and transferred to a hard glass dry test tube, which was placed in an electrically heated sand-bath, the temperature of which was maintained at about 10° higher than the melting point of the phenol. The heating was continued till the evolution of hydrogen chloride had ceased.

The compound obtained was powdered, washed with absolute alcohol and dried.

(b) *Preparation in aqueous solution.*—The method is applicable as the hydrolysis of solutions of manganous chloride is too small for measurement (Bruner, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1900, 32, 133). The phenol was converted into a soluble sodium salt by treating it with sodium hydroxide solution and an aqueous solution of manganous chloride added to it slowly with constant shaking, when phenoxides were precipitated.

The compound obtained was washed free of the excess of manganous chloride first with distilled water and then with alcohol, and dried.

Estimation.—Manganese was estimated gravimetrically as $Mn_2P_2O_7$. Carbon and hydrogen were estimated in three cases by combustion method (Hareas combustion furnace) and in the rest, the organic matter in the compound was found by difference.

TABLE I

Phenols.	Compounds formed.	% Manganese.		% Org. matter.	
		Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
A. Manganous chloride with monohydroxyphenols. $MnCl_2$: phenol = 1 : 2.					
α -Naphthol	Di- α -naphtholato-M*	16.54	16.11	83.46	83.89
	$(C_{10}H_7O)_2Mn$			C : 69.25 H : 4.38	70.39 4.13
β -Naphthol	Di- β -naphtholato-M $(C_{10}O_7)_2Mn$	16.29	16.11	83.71	83.89
<i>o</i> -Nitrophenol	Di- <i>o</i> -nitrophenolato-M $(NO_2.C_6H_4O)_2Mn$	15.59	16.61	84.41	83.39
<i>p</i> -Nitrophenol	Di- <i>p</i> -nitrophenolato-M $(NO_2.C_6H_4O)_2Mn$	15.96	16.61	84.04	83.39
2 : 4-Dinitrophenol	2 : 4-Dinitrophenolato-M $[(NO_2)_2.C_6H_3O]_2Mn$	13.86	13.05	86.14	86.95
2 : 4-Dinitro- α -naphthol	2 : 4-Dinitro- α -naphtholato-M $[(NO_2)_2C_{10}H_6O]_2Mn$	10.87	10.56	89.13	89.44
B. Manganous chloride with dihydroxyphenols. $MnCl_2$: phenol = 1 : 1.					
Resorcinol	Resorcinolato-M	34.30	33.71	65.70	66.29
	$C_6H_4O_2.Mn$			C : 43.42 H : 2.32	44.21 2.47
Pyrocatechol	Pyrocatecholato-M $C_6H_4O_2.Mn$	33.46	33.71	66.54	66.29
Hydroquinone	Hydroquinonato-M $C_6H_4O_2.Mn$	33.59	33.71	66.41	66.29
Phenolphthalein	Phenolphthaleinato-M $C_8H_4.C_2O_2(C_6H_4O)_2Mn$	15.05	14.81	84.95	85.19
Quinhydrone	Quinhydronato-M $C_6H_4O_2.C_6H_4O_2.Mn$	20.57	20.27	79.43	79.73
C. Manganous chloride with trihydroxyphenols. $MnCl_2$: phenol = 3 : 2.					
Pyrogallol	Di-pyrogallolato-3M	40.85	41.55	59.15	58.45
	$(C_6H_3O_3)_2Mn_3$			C : 34.47 H : 1.58	35.08 1.47
Phloroglucinol	Di-phloroglucinolato-3M $(C_6H_3O_3)_2Mn_3$	41.35	41.55	58.65	58.45

*M stands for manganate.

D I S C U S S

Most of the compounds obtained are black in colour, insoluble in water and in common organic solvents. No coloration is obtained with ferric chloride, showing the absence of any phenolic -OH group. These are difficultly soluble in mineral acids and do not melt.

On analysis it is found that chlorine present in $MnCl_2$ has been completely removed and manganese replaces two atoms of the hydrogen in all the compounds studied; *i.e.*, one molecule of manganous chloride reacts with two molecules of a monohydroxyphenol and with one molecule of a dihydroxyphenol; three molecules of manganous chloride combine with two molecules of a trihydroxy phenol, as represented below.

The dihydroxyphenol derivatives are most stable, due probably to the formation of stable five-membered ring with no double bond.

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